

Evaluation of Explainable AI Localisation Performance Using Relevance F-Score

Gregory Balogh, Niall McLaughlin, Austen Rainer

Queen's University Belfast

Abstract

Explainable AI (XAI) has gained significant attention in the AI research community. However, the absence of a standard method for measuring the quality of explanations, and the diversity of existing XAI methodologies, make it hard to compare the performance of different XAI methods. An essential property of image-based XAI methods is their localisation performance, which describes how well the XAI method identifies the relevant object of interest. Existing methods for measuring XAI localisation performance do not consider the full XAI output, including image regions with negative saliency. To address the limitations of existing XAI localisation metrics, we introduce the Relevance F-score (RFS), which considers image regions with both positive and negative saliency to better capture an XAI method's localisation performance. We evaluate our approach using a Visual Question Answering (VQA) network trained on CLEVR-XAI dataset.

Keywords: Explainable AI Evaluation, Computer Vision, Visual Question Answering

1 Introduction

Explainable AI (XAI) has gained substantial attention in research and industry. The effectiveness of XAI methodologies is becoming increasingly important with the emergence of new methods [Huang et al., 2020, Yuan et al., 2020, Wang et al., 2020]. However, evaluating these methods objectively presents a challenge [Krishna et al., 2022, Zhou et al., 2021]. This study focuses on computer vision tasks and uses VQA to compare several XAI methods. The attention maps generated using commonly applied state-of-the-art techniques are analysed, and the inefficiencies of current evaluation metrics are demonstrated. The proposed explanation methods enable the creation of heat maps that portray an image's positive and negative attributions, revealing insights into the neural network's attention. Saliency maps help identify the essential pixels for accurate machine learning predictions. The current metrics only consider the positive attributions of the heat maps while neglecting the negative attributions. This approach limits the applicability of these metrics, as the location of negative attributions can indicate sub-optimal model performance. To overcome this limitation, we apply recall and F-score to assess neural network attention maps comprehensively.

2 Related Work

There exist many ways to evaluate the localisation quality of an explanation based on the location of the feature attributions with respect to the ground truth. Pointing game [Zhang et al., 2018] is a top-down visual attention model which extracts the maximum value on the attention map and assesses its position relative to the ground truth mask. If the attribution and the object of interest overlap, it's a hit; otherwise, it is a miss. The overall accuracy of the XAI method is calculated as the total number of hits relative to all explanations. Since this metric utilises a singular highest-value pixel, it cannot provide enough depth regarding the location of other attributions. Attribution localisation [Kohlbrenner et al., 2020] measures the ratio of positive attributions on the

ground truth mask relative to the total number of positive attributions. Top-K intersection [Theiner et al., 2022] calculates the intersection between the ground truth mask and the location of the top-K (1,000 by default) feature attributions. AUC (Area under the ROC curve) [Fawcett, 2006] compares the ratio of the explanations' true and false positive rates. And Focus [Arias-Duart et al., 2021] quantifies the precision of the explanation by creating mosaics of data instances from different classes. Essentially, it estimates the reliability of explanations using positive salience.

The methods most closely related to our work are Relevance Mass Accuracy and Relevance Rank Accuracy [Arras et al., 2020]. Relevance Mass Accuracy [Arras et al., 2020] computes the ratio of the positively attributed pixels inside the ground truth mask towards the overall positive attributions. Similar to Attribution localisation [Kohlbrenner et al., 2020], Relevance Mass Accuracy is mathematically equivalent to precision. Relevance Rank Accuracy [Arras et al., 2020], sorts the positive attributions of the explanation by their magnitude in descending order and calculates the ratio of the most highly attributed pixels inside the bounding box. Unlike in the Top-K intersection [Theiner et al., 2022], Relevance Rank Accuracy has no static value for the number of attributions to consider. The number of pixels considered is determined by the size of the ground truth mask. Top-K intersection and Relevance Rank Accuracy only consider a subsection of pixels with positive attributions.

The importance of positive attributions is undeniable since these pixels contribute to the prediction. On the other hand, the current metrics do not offer insights based on the location of negative attributions. Negative pixel attributions are features that negatively impact the predictive model performance and can result in an incorrect prediction if they overlap with the object of interest. The negative attributions can be more meaningful if the aim is to understand causes of sub-optimal model performance. The above-mentioned metrics, such as Relevance Mass Accuracy, are mathematically equivalent to precision. However, precision does not consider negative attributions and is inadequate when we have imbalanced classes [Reio Jr, 2016]. In addition, high precision does not automatically translate to accurate predictions or good-quality explanations because the negative attributions, which are not considered, also affect the model's performance. This, in turn, prevents a deeper understanding of the models' attention with respect to the object of interest. In this work, we propose a new method to assess the localisation accuracy of an XAI methods that addresses these limitations.

3 Methodology

In this work, we propose a new way to compare the localisation performance of XAI methods. Our approach is based on comparing the saliency map produced by an XAI method with ground truth information indicating the most important object(s) in the scene. From our review of the literature (See Section 2), we can see it is challenging to compare different XAI methods.

Assume we are given a Visual Question Answering (VQA) model that takes an image as input and produces an answer. Also, assume we have ground truth information indicating the relevant parts of the image needed to answer the question. An XAI method will produce a saliency map showing where the classifier's attention is focused. The saliency map can have positive and negative values, depending on which areas contribute positively or negatively towards the VQA model's final decision. In the ideal case, the positive areas of the saliency map will exactly cover the object(s) of interest and have no overlap with the background or other objects. To evaluate the localisation performance of the XAI method, we measure how well the saliency map matches the relevant object(s) in the ground truth mask. In Fig. 1, we show how the problem of evaluating the localisation performance of an XAI method can be modelled as a classification problem. We assume that for each input, ground truth information is available that specifies the locations of the relevant object(s). Then, for a given saliency map, we can then define true-positive area, true-negative area, false-positive area and false-negative areas as follows:

- **True Positive Area (TPA)** - Regions with a positive saliency value located inside the ground truth mask of the object of interest. These pixels are expected to correspond to the relevant area(s) that the machine learning model should use to make correct predictions.

Q: What colour is the large sphere?

Figure 1: Overview of our method. Areas of positive saliency are green, while areas of negative saliency are red. We treat the problem of XAI evaluation as a classification problem. We define True Positive Area (TPA), True Negative Area (TNA), False Negative Area (FNA) and False Positive Area (FPA) based on the XAI saliency map and the ground truth. Can then evaluate XAI methods performance using Relevance F-score (RFS), which is equivalent to F1-score.

- **True Negative Area (TNA)** - Regions with negative saliency located outside the ground truth mask of the object of interest. These pixels correspond to the irrelevant area(s) that the machine learning model should not use to make correct predictions.
- **False Negative Area (FNA)** - Regions with negative saliency located inside the ground truth mask of the object of interest. These regions are falsely identified as irrelevant.
- **False Positive Area (FPA)** - Regions with a positive saliency value located outside the ground truth mask of the object of interest. These regions are falsely identified as relevant.

In an ideal scenario, we expect all positive attributions to be located on the relevant object identified in the ground truth. And we expect that pixels located outside the ground truth are not required to answer the question, so should have negative or zero saliency. Current approaches to evaluating XAI saliency maps, such as Relevance Mass Accuracy (RMA) and Relevance Rank Accuracy (RRA), tend to ignore the negative saliency values [Arras et al., 2020]. This is because they have a pooling function, such as squaring all saliency values, to make all saliency values positive, which allows easy comparison with the ground-truth mask. RMA is defined as $RMA = R_{\text{within}} / R_{\text{total}}$ i.e., the sum of saliency scores within the ground truth mask, divided by the sum of saliency values in the whole image. Using our definitions above, and ignoring negative attributions, we can see this is equivalent to true-positive pixels divided by the sum of true positives and false positives, i.e. the standard definition of precision. Precision alone cannot fully characterise the performance of a classifier. We address this limitation by introducing the Relevance F-score (RFS).

3.1 Relevance F-Score (RFS)

To address the limitations of existing XAI evaluation methods, we propose to evaluate the localisation performance of XAI methods using a measure based on the F1-score, which we call Relevance F-Score (RFS). A good classifier should have both high precision and high recall. Likewise, a good XAI method with a high RFS, has two desirable properties that correlate with what a human evaluator would expect from a good explanation. Firstly, the model makes a prediction based on the relevant pixels only, i.e., the positive attributions overlap with the object of interest or the ground truth mask. Secondly, negative attributions occur outside the ground

truth mask. We define Relevance F-Score (RFS) as follows:

$$\text{Relevance F-Score} = 2 \frac{P_a R_a}{P_a + R_a} \quad (1)$$

$$P_a = TPA / (TPA + FPA) \quad (2)$$

$$R_a = TPA / (TPA + FNA) \quad (3)$$

Where True Positive Area (TPA), False positive Area (FPA) and False Negative Area (FNA) are defined above (See Section 3 and Fig. 1). We can define P_a and R_a equivalently to precision and recall. Finally, the Relevance F-Score is defined in an equivalent way to F1-score. From this definition, we can see that for RFS to take a high value, both P_a and R_a must take high values. For this to happen the positive area of the saliency map must fall solely within the ground-truth mask of the object of interest, while any negative attributions must fall outside the object of interest.

4 Experiments

In this section, we compare Relevance F-Score (RFS) against the literature. To do this, we evaluate various XAI algorithms on a visual question-answering (VQA) network. We use a Relation Network [Santoro et al., 2017], trained and evaluated on the CLEVR-XAI dataset [Arras et al., 2020], as our VQA model. The final layer of the Relation Network is a softmax with 28 outputs, covering all the possible answers to the CLEVR questions. The model achieves 98% and 90% accuracy on the CLEVR simple and complex questions, respectively. We generate saliency maps for each XAI method using the Captum [Kokhlikyan et al., 2020] XAI framework.

The CLEVR XAI dataset [Arras et al., 2020] consists of 10,000 synthetic images of various geometric objects. It has two sets of queries: simple and complex. The dataset includes questions, answers, and ground truth masks for all questions. CLEVR XAI simple has 39,761 questions and focuses on object attributes related to a single object, such as material, size, shape and colour. It does not include inter-object relational questions, for example, a position of an object relative to another. CLEVR XAI complex includes 100,000 questions related to quantitative, relational, and existential properties of the scene.

4.1 Quantitative Comparison of RFS with the literature

We compare our proposed method, RFS with two existing XAI evaluation methods from the literature Relevance Mass Accuracy and Relevance Rank Accuracy [Arras et al., 2020]. Given a VQA network and the CLEVR dataset; for each prediction in the CLEVR simple and complex sets, we applied six different post-hoc XAI methods: Guided Backprop [Springenberg et al., 2014], Deconvnet [Zeiler and Fergus, 2014], Gradient×Input [Shrikumar et al., 2016], IG [Sundararajan et al., 2017], Gradient [Simonyan et al., 2013]. The resulting explanations are represented as a $128 \times 128 \times 3$ pixel matrix, due to the RGB channels of the original images. To allow comparison with the one-channel ground truth we sum across the RGB channels. This allows negative values to be present in the saliency maps, which are needed for RFS. For Relevance Mass Accuracy (RMA), which requires positive saliency values, we use min-max normalisation.

4.1.1 Simple Protocol

The simple protocol is intended to measure a VQA model’s ability to answer questions related to the attributes of a single object e.g., shape, colour, size or material. To answer these questions, the model only needs to focus on a single object in the scene. We perform several variations of this experiment to measure different aspects of performance. Experiment 1 calculates the localisation metrics with ground truth containing only a single object and when the answer is correctly predicted. This experiment serves as a baseline as we compare the subsequent experiments with the first one. In experiment 2, we report results only for cases where the underlying classifier has high confidence. In experiment 3, we measure the location of the attributions for cases where the object of interest has an area greater than 1,000 pixels. In experiment 4, we use the ground truth

Experiment	RFS	RMA (Ours)	RRA (Ours)	RMA (Original) [Arras et al., 2020]	RRA (Original) [Arras et al., 2020]
	mean	mean	mean	mean	mean
1) Single object, correct answers	0.112	0.070	0.095	0.478	0.384
2) High confidence (>0.99999)	0.129	0.082	0.108	0.502	0.400
3) GT mask > 1,000 pixels	0.112	0.070	0.094	0.714	0.544
4) All objects, correct answers	0.392	0.356	0.282	0.640	0.424
5) Colour only	0.075	0.105	0.120	0.498	0.412

Table 1: Mean RFS, RMA and RRA averaged over all six XAI methods for simple protocol experiments. (Ours) indicates our own implementation of RMA and RRA [Arras et al., 2020].

mask for all objects and include only correctly predicted answers. Finally, in experiment 5, we consider only correctly predicted questions and query an object’s colour. For each experiment, we apply the six XAI methods to explain the predictions of the VQA model. We then measure the similarity between the ground-truth mask and the XAI saliency map produced by each XAI method using RFS and two methods from the literature, RMA and RRA [Arras et al., 2020]. We then average the results across all the XAI methods. In Table 1, we show the results of all our experiments. We also include the results from the same experiments on the original CLEVR-XAI paper [Arras et al., 2020].

The results in Table 1 show that the RFS scores are generally lower in magnitude than the original RMA and RRA scores. This is because RFS considers negative attributions, leading to fewer positive attribution pixels within the ground-truth mask. (We will confirm this by qualitative examination in Section 4.2). Compared to the original RMA and RRA figures, our RMA and RRA figures are produced using min-max normalisation. So we observe that our average RMA and RRA scores are significantly lower than those in the original CLEVR XAI paper and lower than our RFS. We treat Experiment 1 as a baseline. The results of Experiment 2 show that when looking at only correct and high-confidence predictions, the RFS scores are generally higher than the baseline Experiment 1. This indicates that the underlying network emphasises the correct object of interest more. We note that the same is not observed when looking at RMA. With RMA, the average change compared to the baseline experiment is only 5%, whereas, for RFS, the difference is 15%. In Experiment 3, which looks at larger objects, we can see little change in the RFS from the baseline. However, we can see that both RMA and RRA are more sensitive to changes in object size. In the original CLEVR XAI paper RMA and RRA increase by over 40% on average (49% and 42% respectively) relative to the baseline, whereas our mean RMA and RRA scores change significantly less (0.1% and 1.5% respectively). This highlights that our approach is more stable. Looking at the results for Experiment 4, where all objects are used in the ground truth, RFS and our RMA and RRA scores, increase significantly compared to using a single object ground truth, which means that the Relation Network uses several objects to make predictions. On the other hand, the original RMA and RRA scores increase to a smaller extent. In Experiment 5, the mean Relevance F-score, RMA, and RRA all increase. We note that our results differ from those in the CLEVR XAI paper.

4.1.2 Complex Protocol

The complex protocol measures how accurately the model can answer questions related to counting, or spatial relationships between multiple objects. The queries in this experiment are related to multiple objects, so a variety of ground truth masks are used:

- **Unique:** This mask shows the location of a single object that must be uniquely identified among the set of objects present in the scene to answer the question.
- **Unique first non-empty:** This mask identifies one or more objects that are necessary to answer the question correctly. It includes the objects in the question.

XAI Method	Unique		Unique First-n-e.		Union		All Objects	
	RFS	RMA	RFS	RMA	RFS	RMA	RFS	RMA
Guided BProp [Springenberg et al., 2014]	0.23	0.17	0.23	0.17	0.38	0.28	0.46	0.34
Deconvnet [Zeiler and Fergus, 2014]	0.23	0.17	0.23	0.17	0.38	0.28	0.46	0.34
Gradient×Input [Shrikumar et al., 2016]	0.20	0.15	0.16	0.11	0.34	0.25	0.42	0.30
IG [Sundararajan et al., 2017]	0.12	0.08	0.15	0.10	0.25	0.12	0.22	0.14
Gradient [Simonyan et al., 2013]	0.11	0.07	0.14	0.10	0.20	0.13	0.25	0.17

Table 2: Mean RFS and RMA measured across all XAI methods on the CLEVR-XAI-complex dataset. Averaged across all correctly predicted questions that do not involve counting. We discard questions about an object’s existence where the answer is no.

- **Union:** This mask shows the location of all objects that are related to the question.
- **All objects:** This mask includes all objects in the image, regardless of their relevance to the question.

In Table 2, we show the mean RFS score averaged across the correct predictions where the question is not quantitative and where we exclude questions where the answer is ‘no’. The results suggest that XAI methods that use back-propagation, for example, DeConvNet [Zeiler and Fergus, 2014] and Guided Back-propagation [Springenberg et al., 2014], achieve higher RMA, which implies their positive attributions are more concentrated inside the ground truth mask than in gradient-based methods. However, these methods also achieve higher RFS, because backpropagation-based methods have a tendency to generate less noise on the attribution map. In other words, these explanation methods can provide a more accurate representation of positive and negative attributions. On the other hand, simple gradient-based methods that calculate the gradients via a forward pass, including Gradient, Input × Gradient, and Integrated Gradients appear to produce more attributions (Figure 3). As a result, these explanations appear to include significant noise meaning the attributions are visible even if their value is negligible. As a result, they achieve lower RFS.

4.2 Qualitative Evaluation

We now perform a qualitative evaluation to compare RFS with the existing RMA method. This experiment examines explanation saliency maps with different combinations of recall and precision, hence showing qualitatively how RFS varies as the underlying saliency map varies. For each condition, we report the corresponding RFS and RMA values. The saliency maps were produced using Integrated Gradients.

The results in Fig. 2 demonstrate that our proposed method RFS is better able to indicate when the XAI method has correctly localised the relevant object(s). In contrast, we see that when the RMA is high, it does not necessarily indicate that the model is looking at the correct object or that the attributions are concentrated. In addition, the shortcoming of RMA in our example is that it turns negative attributions into positives. However, the RFS uses the location of both positive and negative attributions, providing a better understanding of the underlying functionality of different explainable AI methods. In Fig. 2 we find cases where the RMA is high, but recall is low. This illustrates that RMA is an insufficient evaluation metric whereas RFA requires both precision and recall to be high to achieve a high value. Hence RFA is better at identifying explanations that focus on the object of interest, and hence have a high localisation accuracy, as in the lower right of Fig. 2.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed a new metric, Relevance F-Score, to measure the localisation quality of saliency-map-based XAI methods. Relevance F-Score considers both positive and negative saliency regions to give a more rounded understanding of the localisation performance of different XAI methods. We have evaluated our methods both quantitatively and qualitatively on the CLEVR-XAI dataset. We show that our method is better able to identify which XAI methods have good localisation performance compared to existing

Figure 2: The above examples demonstrate that RFS with min-max normalisation can show the location of negative attributions, leading to a more robust explanation than RMA alone.

Figure 3: This figure illustrates the wide variety of outputs from different XAI methods. From left to right - Guided Backprop, Integrated Gradients, Input \times Gradient and Saliency.

XAI evaluation methods. Our evaluation is made possible by the ground-truth information on the CLEVR-XAI dataset. In future work, we will seek to extend the evaluation of XAI methods to more complex real-world datasets.

References

- [Arias-Duart et al., 2021] Arias-Duart, A., Parés, F., and Garcia-Gasulla, D. (2021). Who explains the explanation? quantitatively assessing feature attribution methods. *CoRR*, abs/2109.15035.
- [Arras et al., 2020] Arras, L., Osman, A., and Samek, W. (2020). Ground truth evaluation of neural network explanations with clevr-xai. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.07258*.
- [Fawcett, 2006] Fawcett, T. (2006). An introduction to roc analysis. *Pattern recognition letters*, 27(8):861–874.
- [Huang et al., 2020] Huang, Q., Yamada, M., Tian, Y., Singh, D., Yin, D., and Chang, Y. (2020). Graphlime: Local interpretable model explanations for graph neural networks. *CoRR*, abs/2001.06216.
- [Kohlbrenner et al., 2020] Kohlbrenner, M., Bauer, A., Nakajima, S., Binder, A., Samek, W., and Lapuschkin, S. (2020). Towards best practice in explaining neural network decisions with lrp. In *2020 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, pages 1–7. IEEE.

- [Kokhlikyan et al., 2020] Kokhlikyan, N., Miglani, V., Martin, M., Wang, E., Alsallakh, B., Reynolds, J., Melnikov, A., Kliushkina, N., Araya, C., Yan, S., et al. (2020). Captum: A unified and generic model interpretability library for pytorch. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.07896*.
- [Krishna et al., 2022] Krishna, S., Han, T., Gu, A., Pombra, J., Jabbari, S., Wu, S., and Lakkaraju, H. (2022). The disagreement problem in explainable machine learning: A practitioner’s perspective. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2202.01602*.
- [Reio Jr, 2016] Reio Jr, T. G. (2016). Nonexperimental research: Strengths, weaknesses and issues of precision. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 40(8/9):676–690.
- [Santoro et al., 2017] Santoro, A., Raposo, D., Barrett, D. G. T., Malinowski, M., Pascanu, R., Battaglia, P. W., and Lillicrap, T. P. (2017). A simple neural network module for relational reasoning. *CoRR*, abs/1706.01427.
- [Shrikumar et al., 2016] Shrikumar, A., Greenside, P., Shcherbina, A., and Kundaje, A. (2016). Not just a black box: Learning important features through propagating activation differences. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1605.01713*.
- [Simonyan et al., 2013] Simonyan, K., Vedaldi, A., and Zisserman, A. (2013). Deep inside convolutional networks: Visualising image classification models and saliency maps. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6034*.
- [Springenberg et al., 2014] Springenberg, J. T., Dosovitskiy, A., Brox, T., and Riedmiller, M. (2014). Striving for simplicity: The all convolutional net. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6806*.
- [Sundararajan et al., 2017] Sundararajan, M., Taly, A., and Yan, Q. (2017). Axiomatic attribution for deep networks. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 3319–3328. PMLR.
- [Theiner et al., 2022] Theiner, J., Müller-Budack, E., and Ewerth, R. (2022). Interpretable semantic photo geolocation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, pages 750–760.
- [Wang et al., 2020] Wang, J., Wiens, J., and Lundberg, S. M. (2020). Shapley flow: A graph-based approach to interpreting model predictions. *CoRR*, abs/2010.14592.
- [Yuan et al., 2020] Yuan, H., Tang, J., Hu, X., and Ji, S. (2020). Xgnn: Towards model-level explanations of graph neural networks. In *Proceedings of the 26th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery Data Mining, KDD ’20*, page 430–438, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [Zeiler and Fergus, 2014] Zeiler, M. D. and Fergus, R. (2014). Visualizing and understanding convolutional networks. In *European conference on computer vision*, pages 818–833. Springer.
- [Zhang et al., 2018] Zhang, J., Bargal, S. A., Lin, Z., Brandt, J., Shen, X., and Sclaroff, S. (2018). Top-down neural attention by excitation backprop. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 126(10):1084–1102.
- [Zhou et al., 2021] Zhou, Y., Booth, S., Ribeiro, M. T., and Shah, J. (2021). Do feature attribution methods correctly attribute features? *CoRR*, abs/2104.14403.